

Effect of chitosan molecular weight of chitosan-citrate film on site specific *in vitro* release of Ofloxacin

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Abstract : Chitosan, a biodegradable and biocompatible polysaccharide, is a potentially useful material in various fields. Chitosan films with different molecular weights (MW) of chitosan were developed followed by incorporation of Ofloxacin as a model drug by a casting/solvent evaporation technique. And citrate cross-linked films were prepared simply by dipping film into sodium citrate solution. The swelling ratio of citrate/chitosan film was sensitive to pH and ionic strength studied here. These films were characterized by release and swelling studies, Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), Optical microscope coupled with Raman spectroscopy, Scanning electron colorimetry (SEM), Drug release based on cross linking time. Concentration of cross linking agent significantly influenced the *in vitro* release of drug as well of swelling of the films. The higher the MW of chitosan lower release rate was observed. The present study showed that MW and cross linking time of films regulated the varying swelling and drug release at pH 3.5 and pH 6.2. In addition, it indicated that the citrate/chitosan films were useful in drug delivery i.e. site-specific controlled drug release in stomach.

Keywords : Chitosan, citrate cross-linking, drug delivery, Ofloxacin, site-specific controlled drug release.

Introduction

Chitosan is the common name of a linear random copolymer of β -(1-4) linked-D-glucosamine whose molecular structure comprises a linear backbone linked through glycosidic bonds. The basic amine groups of this polysaccharide are protonated and thus positively charged in the most physiological fluids. Chitosan is mostly hydrophilic and the percentage of acetylated monomers and their distribution in the chains has a critical effect on its solubility and conformation in aqueous media. Hence chitosan exhibits pH dependent behaviours in solution and some interesting biopharmaceutical properties such as muco-adhesiveness and ability to open, epithelial tight junction. These characteristics of chitosan have attracted many scientists working in biomedical area and particularly in drug delivery¹⁻⁸.

Due to its unique polymeric cationic character, chitosan's gel and film forming properties have been extensively examined in the pharmaceutical industry for its potential in the development of drug delivery system^{9,10,13}.

Chitosan films were usually prepared by chemical cross

lining with glutaraldehyde¹¹ these films remain intact under acidic condition due to the ionization of amino groups but remained in a shrunken state under neutral condition. Moreover, chitosan is reported to have intragastric floating characteristics and prolonged retention of the dosage form in the stomach, by utilizing these advantages chitosan films, or other dosage forms have been exploited widely for oral sustained drug delivery in the stomach^{12,13}. To improve the pH-sensitive performance, blended chitosan films have usually been prepared e.g. polyether oxides films have excellent pH-sensitivity^{14,15}. The chemical cross linking agents generally induce toxicity and other undesirable side effects and to overcome these drawbacks reversible physical cross linking by electrostatic interaction was applied in the preparation of chitosan films¹⁰.

Low molecular weight (MW) ions to prepare an ionic cross linking polymeric matrix was found to be very simple and mild, and cross linking process was achieved by just dipping the polymer films into cross linking ion solution^{14,16}. Anion cross linked film is reported by Shu *et al.*¹⁵. Due to electrostatic interaction between sodium ci-

trate and chitosan, citrate cross-linked chitosan beads or microspheres films may be useful for site specific drug delivery applications. Polymer MW has a major effect on chitosan properties in terms of drug delivery time¹⁷. In the present study we have prepared chitosan-cross linked with sodium citrate films using different MW in order to explore the feasibility of chitosan as a drug carrier. Ofloxacin as a model drug is a synthetic fluoroquinolone (fluoroquinolones) antibacterial agent that inhibits the super coiling activity of bacterial DNA gyrase, halting DNA replication. Ofloxacin is considered to be soluble in aqueous solutions with pH between 2 and 5. It is sparingly to slightly soluble in aqueous solutions with pH 7 (solubility falls to 4 mg/mL) and freely soluble in aqueous solutions with pH above 9. Its molecular mass is 361.3675 and its chemical formula is $C_{18}H_{20}FN_3O_4$. To the best of our knowledge no work on the chitosan-citrate film based drug delivery has been done so far by using this drug. The present work deals with *in vitro* release studies at different pH 3.5 and 6.5 on chitosan/citrate films loaded with different molecular weight chitosan and Ofloxacin a model drug were characterized by swelling studies, DSC, Optical microscope coupled with Raman spectroscopy, SEM and drug release patterns were studied for their site specific drug delivery as well as polymer morphology.

Results and discussion

Chitosan and citrate interaction :

Citrate is anionic in nature containing three carboxylic groups in its structure whereas chitosan is polysaccharide due to its unique polymeric cationic character. The preparation of cross linking chitosan with anionic citrate was found to be simpler because charge density of citrate and chitosan is controlled by solution pH. The ionization of citrate mainly depends on solution pH because weak citric acid under neutral and weakly acidic conditions decreases the solution pH leading to lower degree of ionization of citrate. In the case of chitosan being a weak polybase, degree of ionization decreases with solution pH above 6.5.

The turbidimetric curve of sodium citrate and chitosan shows that at pH 1–4.5 solution was very clear because of low charge density of citrate. There after increase in pH of the solution the solution became turbid because most of the amino groups protonated to NH_3^+ at pH 1.2–2.8 in

the presence of strong acids. On the other hand most of the carboxylic groups yielded a double break due to salt formation with excess amino group at which most of carboxyl groups changed to unprotonated form¹⁹. Increasing pH is favourable for improving acylation reaction between citrate and chitosan and more amine groups participated in the reaction at higher pH than the lower pH indicating higher reaction extent could be obtained when increasing pH from 4.5 to 9¹⁹. The results of the present study (Fig. 1) also support to the above findings. This is because if the alkali added was not enough and the reaction was taken place at a lower pH. The amino groups were proto-

Fig. 1. Turbidity titration curves of chitosan/citrate solution at 420 nm, citrate = green, chitosan = blue.

nated under acidic conditions and therefore it was difficult for the positively charged amine of chitosan to react with partially charged carbonyl group carbon in carboxylic acid. Normally amine groups are less likely to carry positive charges and therefore they could attack the carbonyl carbon of the carboxyl groups forming readily amide linkage via amidation. However, in ambient temperature the interaction between chitosan and carboxylic acid is associated with electrostatic reaction between the protonated amino group in the chitosan backbone and carboxylate ion in the carboxylic acid in aqueous solutions as it forms salt and causes turbidity²⁰.

Physical characterization of chitosan/citrate films :

Swelling index :

The films prepared by different molecular weight of chitosan were kept in two buffer solutions of pH 3.5 and pH 6.5 respectively and allowed to swell for 30 h at room temperature. It was found that all three different MW chitosan-citrate films were significantly affected and swelled

more at pH 3.5 compared to pH 6.5 due to dissociation of ionic cross linking and repelling interaction between negatively charged carboxylic group and also due to weakened salt bonds at higher pH 6.5. Maximum swelling was observed at about 5 h of exposure (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Swelling ratio of chitosan/citrate films (high MW = blue, medium MW = red, low MW = green) at pH 3.5.

Thickness of the chitosan/citrate films :

Table 1 shows the mean thickness (mean \pm SD, n = 5) and drug content of the films prepared at varying ratio of cross linking agent sodium citrate and time. In the present study experimental results are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) and students *t*-test was applied to observe significant differences in drug release from the films and differences were considered to be statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. The mean thickness of the films of different chitosan MW was measured and found within the range of 46.7 to 47.4 μ m and there was no significant variation in the thickness of the films and drug content uniformity of different MW films was observed in the range of 98.79% to 100%. The results indicate that the process employed to prepare films in the present work is capable of producing films of uniform drug content with minimum variation. There was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between the films in terms of drug content.

Chemical characterization of chitosan/citrate films :

DSC thermogram is a possible method to determine the modification in drug. Fig. 3 shows DSC thermograms of pure drug. The DSC study of pure drug shows a sharp endothermic peak at 281 $^{\circ}$ C which indicates melting transition of the drug. Blank chitosan films show a broad endothermic peak at about 109 $^{\circ}$ C and exothermic peak at

Table 1. Mean thickness and drug content of different cross-linked chitosan films

Film code	V_1 (h)	V_0 (%)	Film thickness (μ m, n = 5)	Drug (%)
Low molecular weight :				
A1	-	-	46.7 \pm 1.3	100.0
A2	0.50	0.5	50.0 \pm 0.7	100.0
A3	0.50	5	46.9 \pm 0.3	98.33
A4	3.0	0.5	48.6 \pm 1.2	98.23
A5	3.0	5	41.5 \pm 1.6	98.85
Medium molecular weight :				
A6	-	-	46.4 \pm 1.6	100.20
A7	0.50	0.5	42.4 \pm 1.1	100.41
A8	0.50	5	50.4 \pm 1.1	98.93
A9	3.0	0.50	52.6 \pm 1.5	99.23
A10	3.0	5	47.6 \pm 1.4	99.33
High molecular weight :				
A11	-	-	43.6 \pm 1.1	98.64
A12	0.50	0.5	42.9 \pm 1.1	98.89
A13	0.50	5	47.6 \pm 1.5	98.99
A14	3.0	0.50	45.9 \pm 1.3	98.67
A15	3.0	5	47.4 \pm 0.8	98.79

where V_1 (h), cross linking time in h; V_0 (%), cross linking percentage.

about 261 $^{\circ}$ C and endothermic peak was not seen for drug film. This may be due to amorphous state of films and also due to weak interaction between the amino group of chitosan and hydroxyl group of the drug. In this case micronized drug particles may exist between the polymer chains. These results indicate that the chitosan film swelling is larger due to surface wettability and as a result there is higher water penetration within the matrix. The water molecules which present in such system help in the formation of additional hydrogen bond; hence the chitosan in the drug-loaded film degrades in higher temperature than in the blank chitosan film.

Optical microscopy coupled with Raman spectroscopy :

Raman spectroscopic technique is proved to be helpful technique in the chemical characterization of drug solid dispersion and in particular drug polymorphism. In the present study the results suggest that the drug is dispersed in molecular level inside the polymer matrix (Figs. 4B, 4C, 4D drug loaded with different MW chitosan as compared with plain film Fig. 4A). This was further confirmed by comparing Raman spectra of drug loaded

Fig. 3. DSC thermogram of pure drug (sample) and chitosan films A-1, A-6 and A-11.

Fig. 4. Pictures of chitosan-citrate film using optical microscope coupled with Raman spectra : (A) Plain chitosan-citrate film, (B) Chitosan-citrate film loaded with drug A-2, (C) Chitosan-citrate film loaded with drug A-10, (D) Chitosan-citrate film loaded with drug A-15.

chitosan/citrate film (Fig. 5). These observations agree with the result obtained by SEM measurement, suggesting the drug is completely dispersed in the polymeric matrix¹².

SEM analysis :

Analysis of the morphologies of chitosan/citrate films are shown in Fig. 5A. The bottom surfaces of the chitosan/citrate films are very smooth while the upper surface was relatively rough. The surface cross section morphologies have changed significantly due to the incorporation of drugs into the chitosan/citrate film. Large pores were seen on both bottom and upper surface of Ofloxacin loaded films and cross section is very rough and many deficiencies are

observed (Fig. 5B). The results obtained indicate good compatibility between the matrix and the drug Ofloxacin.

In vitro drug release :

The model drug *in vitro* release behaviours from drug loaded chitosan/citrate films in physiological conditions are shown in Fig. 6. Since the release of a bioactive agent from a biodegradable polymeric delivery system is primarily controlled by diffusion of the bioactive agent through the polymer and degradation of the polymer, the release profile with three phases usually is seen for biodegradable polymers i.e. initial period of burst release which is related to the rapid diffusion of the active agent located close to surface of the polymer; second phase of minimal

Fig. 5. Raman spectra of chitosan/citrate films (plain), chitosan/citrate film loaded with drug (low MW chitosan) A-5, film loaded with drug (medium MW chitosan) A-10, film loaded with drug (high MW chitosan) A-15.

release during which the polymer is gradually degraded sufficiently in MW to lead an increase release rate and the third phase with the increase release rate which results from the massive degradation of the polymer. Moreover the release behaviours of a biodegradable polymeric delivery system were influenced by the molecular size of the bioactive agent, polymer composition, MW, the dimension and shape of the matrix, cross linking time and concentration, pH of the solution. Fig. 6 shows that Ofloxacin was released rapidly from the films at pH 3.5. The results indicate that drug release rate decreased significantly at pH 3.5 as chitosan MW increased. Fig. 7 at pH 6.5 indicates drug release was significantly decreased by cross linking agent in our study. It shows that greater the cross linking time lower was the drug release rate.

Experimental

Materials and reagents :

Ofloxacin (USP grade); chitosan low MW (Sigma Aldrich, USA), chitosan medium MW (Sigma Aldrich,

Iceland), chitosan high MW (Sigma Aldrich, Belgium); sodium citrate, glacial acetic acid (AR) and sodium hydroxides were purchased from sd Fine Chemicals (Chennai, India). All other chemicals used were of analytical grades and double distilled water was used throughout the study.

Instrumental :

DSC, DSC Q 1000V9.4 Build 287, Opical microscope coupled with Raman spectroscopy Lesser 536 Aglitrion USA, SEM-FEI Quanta FEG 200-high resolution scanning electron microscope.

Experiment :

Turbidimetric titration :

The interaction between sodium citrate and chitosan was investigated by turbidimetric titration as per reported method¹⁷. In brief, a solution (0.2 g/L sodium citrate and 0.2 g/L chitosan) was prepared at pH 1.0. The titrant (0.2 M NaOH) was delivered using a micro burette into 100 mL chitosan/citrate solution with continuous stirring at ambient temperature until a stable reading was obtained at

Fig. 6. SEM microgram of chitosan/citrate film : (A) Plain chitosan/citrate film, (B) Chitosan/citrate film with loaded drug.

Fig. 7. Release curves of Ofloxacin from chitosan/citrate films at pH 3.5. Details of different codes are provided in Table 1.

Fig. 8. Release curves of Ofloxacin from chitosan/citrate films at pH 6.5. Details of different codes are provided in Table 1.

27 ± 0.5 °C and pH was monitored by a digital pH meter (MK-VI, Systronic, India) with a precision of ± 0.01 . The changes in the turbidity were monitored at 420 nm with a UV-Visible spectrophotometer against a solution (0.2 g/L sodium citrate and 0.2 g/L chitosan) with 100% transmittance. Turbidity values are given as a function of pH of the solution.

Preparation of cross-linked chitosan films :

Chitosan films were prepared by casting/solvent evaporation technique. Solution of chitosan (2 wt%) was prepared with 2 wt% acetic acid solution and then dispersing 0.5 wt% model drug into the system. The same procedure was followed for different MW grade of chitosan. The above solution stand until taped air bubbles were removed and then poured on a glass plate (having area 10×10 cm²). The solution was allowed to dry in a hot air oven (Technico India) at 37 ± 2 °C and then further dried under vacuum at room temperature until constant weight. Dry films were cut into 2×2 cm² and soaked in 100 mL of aqueous sodium citrate solution at 4 °C. The cross linking condition was 2.0–1.0% (w/v) sodium citrate solution (pH 5–7) and cross linking time was 0.5–4.0 h. The chitosan cross-linked with citrate formed were then thoroughly washed with distilled water and transferred to glass plate and dried in hot air oven at 37 °C to a constant weight till films get dried.

The model drug Ofloxacin loss during cross-linking process was determined by UV-Visible absorption at 327 nm (Jasco UV-Visible NIR spectrophotometer Model-V-670 PC).

Physical characterization of chitosan/citrate films :

Swelling index :

The swelling index of chitosan/citrate films after exposure to different pH was determined by sequentially immersing the different films at pH 3.5 (phosphate buffer) and pH 6.5 (acetate buffer) respectively. The swelling index was calculated as $\text{Swelling index} = (W_1 - W_2) / W_1$,

where W_1 is the initial weight of the film and W_2 is the weight of the swollen films.

Thickness of the chitosan/citrate films :

A micrometer was used to measure the thickness of the films and that was expressed as mean of five measurements across each film specimen. To determine weight uniformity of each film five specimens of size $2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$ were weighed on the electronic balance and mean weight was calculated.

Determination of drug content :

The concentration of Ofloxacin in all the cross-linked films was determined spectrophotometry¹⁸. Chitosan/citrate film ($2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$) was weighed accurately and transferred into a 100 mL standard volumetric flask and made to the mark with double distilled water and allowed overnight with constant stirring to allow total release of the drug from the films. After filtering the solution filtrate was assayed by UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 327 nm and the percentage of drug content was calculated by the following equation :

$$\text{Drug content (\%w/w)} = (\text{mass of drug} \times 100) / \text{mass of film.}$$

Statistical analysis :

All experiments were done in triplicate and results were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. One way analysis of variance was performed to assess statistical significance among the data. Results with $p < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

Characterization of chitosan/citrate films :

DSC analysis :

Dry chitosan/citrate films containing different MW of chitosan were subjected to DSC analysis (0–400 °C) employing heating at a rate of 10 °C/min (DSC Q 1000V9.4 Build 287).

Optical microscopy coupled with Raman spectroscopy :

Raman studies on chitosan/citrate films were performed by using micro-Raman spectrometer (Lesser 536 Aglutron USA) equipped with camera microscope system. Experiment was performed at room temperature under the following conditions of 100X microscope objective 200 μm slit width and 5 s exposure time after spreading sample flat on a glass microscope slide.

SEM analysis :

The surface and cross sectional morphologies of

chitosan/citrate films were examined using high resolution scanning electron microscopy (HRSEM) (FEI Quanta FEG 200-high resolution scanning electron microscope).

In vitro drug release :

The model drug release from chitosan/citrate films was performed under the same conditions described in the swelling studies. Drug release from each formulation was performed using USP XXII dissolution method in the simulated gastrointestinal condition by pH change method at 37 °C. pH 3.2 of the media was chosen to represent the gastric condition and pH 6.6 was a compromise condition between the pH of the gastric and the small intestine, and the condition of small intestine was by pH 7.4. 5 mL of each sample was withdrawn from the medium at various time intervals and the medium replenished immediately with the same volume of fresh medium. The release rate of chitosan/citrate was assayed by UV-Visible spectrophotometry at 327 nm.

Conclusion

The present study was to explore the physical-chemical properties of chitosan/citrate films. The results suggest the role of sodium citrate as cross-linking agent and also concentration of sodium citrate which greatly affects the drug release profiles of Ofloxacin. Prepared films had pH sensitive swelling and controlled drug release. The chemical and morphological characterization have showed that there is a good compatibility between matrix film and drug due to strong interactions, namely hydrogen and ionic interaction using higher concentration and lower pH 3.5 of sodium citrate resulting in less swelling and slower drug release. There was no significant difference between low and medium MW of chitosan/citrate film release rate compared to high MW chitosan/citrate film where very small changes in drug release was observed in acidic environment. The results of the present study ensure the scopes of this type of materials for various pharmaceutical purposes film based delivery systems and tablet coating for modified drug release.

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